

ISic0095

Statue base for Gnaeus Pollienus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

breccia (di San Marco)

Object

statue base

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Autopsy

Prag, 2018-07-10

Last Change

2021-01-06 - Jonathan Prag edited on the basis of autopsy notes and photographs

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found at the end of October 1879 on the 'piano della chiesa maggiore e vicino al diruto castello'

Coordinates

37.9879763, 13.6964236

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 123

Physical Description

A tall base of pink veined breccia, finished on all four sides with moulding top and bottom. The upper surface has a circular hole to the rear left (approx. 6cm diameter) and a foot hole (approx 25 x 5 cm) front right. There is light damage to the lower moulding on the rear corners and to the upper moulding on all sides. The base is D 85 cm x W 84 cm; the top is D 71.7 cm x W 64 cm (damaged). The pillar (H 84.5 cm) narrows slightly towards the top (D 51.5 cm to 48.2 cm; W 52 cm to 49 cm). Total height is 125.5 cm.

Dimensions

Height 125.5 cm

Width 84 cm

Depth 85 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin letters, centred on the upper part of the front face of the base.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply v-cut letters with minimal serifs and somewhat uneven in both height and width. Small triangular interpuncts throughout. C, O, G consistently large/wide. P is open, R is closed. E has equal bars.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 48-58 mm

Line 2: 42-48 mm

Line 3: 40-44 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 30-35 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 32 mm

Text

1. Cn(aeo) · Pollieno · Cn(aei) f(ilio)
2. tr(ibunus) · mil(itum) ·
3. legio(nis) · XII

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

To Gnaeus Pollienus, son of Gnaeus, military tribune of the 12th legion

Commentary

This individual is also honoured in ISic0096 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0096>] , found in Termini in 1876. It is suggested also (e.g. Wilson 1990: 42 n.87) that this man is the son of the Pollienus honoured at Haluntium, possibly in the civil war period (ISic1190 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1190>]). A further inscription (ISic0098 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0098>]) records another (anonymous) individual from the same Legio XII Fulminata. The multiple references to this legion encourage the hypothesis that it was veterans of this legion which were settled in the colonial foundation of Augustus in 21 BC (so, e.g., Manganaro 1988: 42). The distinctive breccia from the area of San Marco d'Alunzio suggests a deliberate choice of prestigious material.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285209

EDR 127010

EDCS 22100050

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0095>

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Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7349 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650796>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 13

Dessau, H. 1892-1916. *Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae.* Berlin. At 5093

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 287

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. *Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman*

province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 38-39 n.57 fig.31

Wilson, R.J.A. 1988. Towns of Sicily during the Roman Empire. *Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischer Welt*. 2.11.1: 90-206. At 97

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 42 tav.XI.18

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